

Impacts of Conventional and Contextual Passages on Reading Comprehension of Nomadic Pupils at Inferential Level in Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study investigated the impacts of conventional and contextual English passages on the inferential reading comprehension of Nomadic primary five pupils in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The study had one objective, one research question and a corresponding hypothesis. A pre-test–post-test true experimental design was adopted, with a population of 285 pupils from Nomadic schools in Soba and Sabon-Gari Local Government Areas. Multi-stage sampling techniques, including purposive and random sampling, were used to select participants. Data were collected using the English Reading Achievement Test (ERAT), which was validated by English language experts and had a reliability index of 0.69, considered adequate (Kerlinger, 1973). A pilot study was conducted at Anguwan Nafara Nomadic Primary School, Sabon-Gari Local Government Area. Data were analyzed using mean scores to answer the research question, while t-tests independent statistics was employed to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 significance Alfa level of significance. The findings revealed no significant difference between the reading comprehension of pupils exposed to conventional and contextual passages in the experimental and control groups. The study concluded that incorporating both conventional and culture-specific contextual textbooks enhances the teaching of reading comprehension to Nomadic pupils. This dual approach supports second-language learning and promotes improved academic performance across the curriculum. The study recommends the integration of both conventional and culturally relevant materials in English textbooks to address the unique learning needs of Nomadic pupils, thereby fostering better comprehension and overall academic success.

Keyword: Conventional, Contextual, Reading, Nomadic, Fulbe.

Introduction

The Nigerian government emphasizes education as a fundamental instrument for uplifting the socio-economic conditions of rural populations. This is particularly critical for nomadic groups, such as the Fulani, who face unique challenges in accessing conventional education due to their mobility. To address these challenges, the contextualization of textbooks for nomadic education has been implemented to integrate Fulbe nomads into national development. This approach provides relevant and functional basic education designed to enhance their quality of life and contribute meaningfully to national progress. The Fulbe nomads are primarily itinerant people who migrate in search of livelihoods, often across different regions. According to Ezeomah (1987), they are “ethnic or socio-cultural groups who travel and migrate in large or small groups within a community in search of livelihood.” Other nomadic groups include pastoralists, migrant fishermen, and migrant farmers, all of whom share a transitory lifestyle that complicates traditional educational delivery. These challenges necessitate innovative educational strategies to bridge the gap and ensure equitable access to learning. This study investigates the impact of conventional versus contextual reading passages on the inferential comprehension skills of nomadic pupils in Kaduna State, Nigeria. It seeks to assess how these approaches enhance reading comprehension and facilitate cognitive development, thus enabling nomadic learners to integrate more effectively into broader socio-economic frameworks.

The Nomadic Commission modified the strategy of using content and concept of the nomadic Curriculum and textbooks depicting the socio-cultural background of the nomads. The Commission dropped the conventional English textbooks to make learning more meaningful and easier to the nomads. However, little or no consideration was given to the global nature of education and the future of the nomads. While contextual textbooks are not used by tertiary institutions, nomadic children

are constrained in knowledge at the end of the day; it is likely that nomadic pupils might be restricted to only their environment. Because the world has now turned into a global village, is it not vital to blend the nomads with the outside world? This study therefore explores the Impacts of Conventional and Contextual Passages on Reading Comprehension of Nomadic Pupils at Inferential Level in Kaduna State.

Objectives of the study

The study seeks to achieve the objectives following objectives:

1. The study seeks to examine the differences in the performance of nomadic pupils exposed to reading comprehension in the contextual and conventional passages at the inferential level.

Research Questions

The study intend to answer the question below:

1. What is the difference between the performance of nomadic pupils exposed to reading comprehension in the contextual and conventional passages at inferential level?

Hypotheses

The hypothesis is formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the performance of nomadic pupils exposed to reading comprehension in the contextual and conventional passages at inferential level.

Education is widely recognized as a transformative process that fosters the holistic development of individuals physically, mentally, morally, socially, and technologically. As a cornerstone of societal advancement, education is instrumental in shaping both individuals and the collective trajectory of a nation (Federal Ministry of Education, 2021). Consequently, no segment of society should be excluded from access to education. In this context, nomadic education holds significant relevance to national development, particularly in Nigeria, where nomads constitute a vital part of the population. Nomadic education is not merely a developmental tool for this community but also an essential component of the country's broader efforts toward inclusive and equitable progress (UNESCO, 2021).

However, the provision of education for the nomadic population in Nigeria faces unique and complex challenges. Key among these challenges are the perennial migration of nomads, especially pastoralists, in search of water and pasture; the irrelevance of a sedentary-based school curriculum that fails to address the specific educational needs of nomadic communities; the geographical isolation of nomads, who often reside in remote and inaccessible areas; and structural issues such as land-tenure systems, which hinder settlement and educational accessibility (National Commission for Nomadic Education [NCNE], 2020). These factors collectively impede the delivery of effective education to nomadic populations, underscoring the necessity for tailored interventions (World Bank, 2022). Recognizing the importance of bridging this educational gap, the Nigerian government launched the Nomadic Education Program (NEP). The program was institutionalized with the establishment of the National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) through Decree 41 of December 1989. The NCNE was tasked with implementing strategies to provide the nomadic population with relevant and functional education. The program's goals include equipping nomads with basic education to enhance their survival skills, improving their productivity and income levels, and enabling their active participation in the socio-economic and political life of the nation (Federal Ministry of Education, 2021). Since its inception, the NCNE has initiated various distinct programs to meet the basic education needs of Nigeria's nomadic communities. These programs focus on curriculum contextualization, mobile schooling systems, and capacity-building efforts aimed at addressing the specific educational challenges faced by this group. Despite these efforts, funding constraints and inconsistent governmental commitment have limited the full realization of the program's objectives, highlighting the need for sustained and innovative approaches to nomadic education in Nigeria (NCNE, 2020).

Conventional reading is a formal reading style, used by many academic disciplines, that has a specific set of rules governing grammar, proper use and organization. Conventional reading is, reading taught in academic settings. Conventional method of teaching reading comprehension in nomadic school was practiced right from the inception of the programme where the national curriculum and textual materials for the conventional schools were used. The initial approach to nomadic education in Nigeria faced significant challenges due to its misalignment with the nomads' unique lifestyle. This misalignment was evident in the curriculum content, which did not resonate with the cultural and practical realities of nomadic communities. As a result, the educational programs failed to engage nomadic learners effectively, leading to low attendance and retention rates (Aliyu, 2020).

In the same vein, the nomadic school structure was operated the same as the conventional schools. The school approach, focused on the children of nomadic Fulani community was too conventional for them. Whether they like it or not,

Sedentarisation is their ultimate fate. It follows therefore, that the type of conventional schools' set up for sedentary groups is the one that suits them most particularly, when their inevitable future (Sedentarisation) is borne in mind. Ardo (1986) stated that it is clear that in the long run the pastoralists cannot escape the process of Sedentarisation and further argues that "for the pastoralists to have access to social amenities such as health care, education, and so forth, the question of Sedentarisation always presents itself as a permanent solution. Also, Alkali (1986:4) reiterates his firm belief in the inevitability and suitability of Sedentarisation:

The only answer for giving nomads any kind of education is settling them, and the earlier the better ... let the state or federal governments first and foremost, earmarks land, water and technical know-how for rapid production of pasture. With these the nomads will in the first place stay in the place provided since two aspects that are causing them to move from one place to another are water and pasture.

The structure of nomadic schools has historically mirrored conventional schooling, a model that proved inadequate for the unique lifestyle of the nomadic Fulani community. The educational approach was overly conventional, failing to consider the inevitability of sedentarization as the ultimate outcome for nomads. Studies have shown that sedentarization is essential for pastoralists to access social amenities such as healthcare and education (Abubakar, 2021). Furthermore, the government's role in providing resources such as land, water, and infrastructure has been identified as critical to supporting the settlement of nomads and ensuring stability (Yusuf et al., 2022). To address these challenges, the National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) introduced a contextual approach. This initiative aimed to align curriculum and textual materials with the culture and norms of nomads, recognizing that conventional curricula did not resonate with their realities (Aliyu, 2020). Contextual learning theory, as described by Johnstone et al. (2021), emphasizes the integration of diverse experiences—social, cultural, physical, and psychological into learning environments to help students connect abstract concepts to practical applications.

Reading comprehension has been defined as the process of constructing meaning from text, requiring readers to synthesize written material with their prior knowledge and experiences (Adewumi & Ibrahim, 2023). Scholars have emphasized the need for culturally responsive teaching methods, particularly for nomadic communities. Historically, oral literature has served as a foundational tool for literacy among the Fulani, blending with formal reading activities to facilitate comprehension (Usman, 2020). Critics have argued that traditional teaching methods in nomadic schools lack cultural relevance. In response, the 1969 National Curriculum Conference emphasized that education should reflect societal needs and aspirations (Aliyu, 2020). Collaborative research conducted between 2020 and 2022 has provided further evidence supporting the adaptation of curriculum materials to the socio-economic and cultural realities of nomadic communities (Adewale et al., 2022). NCNE has since partnered with local universities to develop subject-specific materials tailored to nomads, including English, Mathematics, and Social Studies. The importance of literacy for nomadic children extends beyond functionality. It is crucial for civic engagement, enabling them to participate in national socio-political processes by understanding ballot instructions or public information (Yusuf et al., 2022). Reading comprehension thus remains central to nomadic education, highlighting its vital role in achieving functional literacy and fostering socio-economic inclusion.

Methodology

This research employed a pre-test–post-test true experimental design to determine the impact of conventional and contextual textbooks on the reading performance of nomadic pupils. Both the experimental and control groups were pre-tested before the administration of treatment. The experimental group was taught using conventional textbooks, while the control group was taught using contextual textbooks. A post-test was subsequently administered to measure the students' achievements in the concepts taught. The population for the study comprised all primary five pupils in the twelve (12) public nomadic primary schools within Sabon-Gari and Soba Local Education Authorities. The total population of primary five pupils across these schools was 285. The study adopted a multi-stage sampling technique, which involved purposive and simple random sampling methods. The purposive sampling was applied due to the quasi-experimental design, which necessitated a manageable sample size. Simple random sampling was employed to ensure objectivity and eliminate bias. Two schools were selected from each local government area. In line with sample size determination guidelines for experimental studies (e.g., Ferguson, 1970; Frankel & Wallen, 2000), forty (40) pupils were selected for each group, resulting in a total sample size of eighty (80) pupils, which represented 28.1% of the population. Both the experimental and control groups underwent a pre-test to establish baseline knowledge of reading comprehension. The test was designed to evaluate their English reading skills using the English Reading Achievement Test (ERAT). The control group was taught reading comprehension using contextual passages embedded within their textbooks. The experimental group received lessons using both contextual and conventional passages to explore any synergistic effect on their reading comprehension.

After completing the treatment, a post-test was administered to both groups. This test, aligned with the ERAT framework, was designed to measure the pupils' progress and the impact of the different teaching methods. The pre-test and post-test scores were analyzed to determine the effectiveness of contextual textbooks compared to conventional textbooks in enhancing reading performance among nomadic pupils. The analysis utilized statistical tools such as mean scores and t-tests, were used to ascertain significant differences in the pupils' reading achievements across the groups. The quasi-experimental design was chosen because it allows for the examination of cause-and-effect relationships in natural educational settings, where random assignment is impractical (Creswell & Creswell, 2020). The use of contextual textbooks aligns with contemporary approaches to culturally responsive education (Johnstone et al., 2021), while the comparative analysis highlights the potential advantages of integrating local cultural contexts into teaching resources for nomadic education (Adewumi & Ibrahim, 2023).

Results

This section presents the analysis of data collected and findings based on research questions and hypothesis. The scores were analyzed using independent t-test. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the two assessments are presented according to the research question.

Research Question 1

Research Question: What is the difference between the performance of nomadic pupils exposed to reading comprehension in contextual and conventional passages at an inferential level?

Table 1 presents the frequencies of correct and wrong scores on the comprehension of the contextual and conventional passages at the inferential level before and after the treatment. Frequency and percentage of the assessments scores before and after the treatment were used to answer the research question.

Table 1: Frequency of correct and wrong scores on the comprehension of the contextual and conventional passages at the inferential level before and after the experiment

	Inferential level of comprehension	Pre-test				Post-test			
		Correct answers		Wrong answers		Correct answers		Wrong answers	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Control (Contextual) Passages	Why did you think that Dikko has no option than to stay in the village?	15	37.5	25	62.5	20	50.0	20	50
	Did the bridegroom share the Kolanuts himself?	29	72.5	11	27.5	29	72.5	11	27.5
	What happened to the five US bombers on 5 December 1945?	28	70.0	12	30	35	87.5	5	12.5
Experimental (Conventional)	Is the Itemizer dangerous to the body?	27	67.5	13	32.5	30	75.0	10	25.0

Source: Researchers field work 2024

The table revealed a consistent improved comprehension of the pupils who were exposed to the conventional passages. The frequencies of the correct answer (Strange village passage) for the first item for example rose from 15 (37.5%) before the treatment to 20 (50.0%) after the treatment. The same number of pupils who were able to comprehend the correct answer on whether the bridegroom shared the Kola nuts himself (marriage ceremony passage) or not did not change after the treatment. The pupils were 29 or (72.5%) before and 29 (72.5%) after the treatment. The comprehension of the conventional passages improved more among the pupils before and after the treatment. On the passage (The Bermuda Triangle) 28 (70.0%) were able

to comprehend what happened to the five US bombers on 5th December 1945 before the treatment, after the treatment, the number of pupils who comprehended the passage rose to 35 (87.5%) and on the passage on Airport security, the comprehension rose from 27 (67.5%) before the treatment to 30 or 75.0% after the treatment. This general improvement obtained at the inferential level of performances among the pupils was not really the same as what was obtained among those exposed to the contextual passages. The indication here is that the conventional passages tended to have more comprehensive impact on the pupils than was observed from the contextual passages. The significance of the variability observed in the performances is subject to statistical test in the related hypothesis. And answer the research question.

Hypothesis 1

Test of Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the performances of nomadic pupils exposed to reading comprehension in the contextual and conventional passages at the inferential level in Sabon-Gari and Soba local government area of Kaduna state. This hypothesis was tested with the two-sample t-test procedure. The result is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Two sample t-test on performance of nomadic pupils exposed to reading comprehension in the contextual and conventional passages at the inferential level after the experiment.

Status	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	t-value	DF	P-value
Contextual	40	1.25	0.684	0.077	2.899	78	.005
Conventional	40	1.50	0.595	0.067			

(Critical value = 2.00)

Source: Researchers field work 2024

Table 2 reveals that, the pupils who were exposed to the conventional passages had a higher comprehension rate at the inferential level than those exposed to the contextual passages. The observed probability level of significance for the test is 0.005, which is less than $P < 0.05$. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The result revealed that the performances of the pupils who were exposed to the conventional passages were significantly better than that of the pupils who were exposed to the contextual passages after the experiment. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This implies that the use of conventional passage have more enhancing impact on the comprehension of the Nomadic pupils at the inferential level than the use of contextual passages. The finding here is consistent with Olaofe (2007) who pointed out that the writer does not really convey ideas to stimulate him to construct them out of his own experiences and that the one who takes the most to the printed page gains the most. This is reflected in the inferential level of comprehension by the pupils in this finding.

Conclusion

This study revealed that the use of conventional textbooks have significant impact on the reading comprehension among Nomadic pupils in English Language at the inferential level. The finding is therefore a breakthrough in the process of enhancing reading comprehension in English language texts among Nomadic pupils in Nomadic schools within the study area.

Recommendations

The study recommends for the National Commission for Nomadic Education to collaborates with the Ministry of Education to supply the necessary conventional textbooks and other conventional teaching materials to nomadic schools and also the curriculum planners too should take that into cognizance, as well as the nomadic teachers in planning and deliverance of lessons in order to enhance reading Comprehension performance in nomadic schools.

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